

1. The Medical Scenarios

Overview

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Medical Scenario 2	Anaphylactic reaction with obstructed airway - No staff in the red area
Medical Scenario 3	Multi- Organ dysfunction (Hypoxia and septic shock) in pediatric patient
Medical Scenario 4	Receiving an ambulance car with a simple walking patient
Medical Scenario 5	Receiving an ambulance car with a complex patient on a wheel chair
Medical Scenario 6	Panic attack within the red area entering the patient room from outside
Medical Scenario 7	Intubated patient in delirium
Medical Scenario 8	Hypoxia due to failure of the ventilator after a power breakdown
Medical Scenario 9	Critical neonate with difficulties in breathing
Medical Scenario 10	Atone hemorrhage with hemodynamic instability
Medical Scenario 11	Emergency Cesarean section
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Medical Scenario 14	Septic shock with critical hypotension – C- Problem
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Medical Scenario 16	Evacuation of an unconscious patient
Medical Scenario 17	Acute kidney and liver injury requiring intervention (hemodialysis)

Medical Scenario 1: Anaphylactic reaction with obstructed airway / circulatory problems

Medical Scenario 1		Anaphylaxis																																																										
 Patient information	Anna Awasse	Age Height Weight	46 y 160 cm 75 kg																																																									
 Briefing	<p>You are a team of 2 physicians and 2 nurses within in the green area. A 46-year-old female patient is isolated in the unit with confirmed infection with pathogen X (airborne transmission) on day 5 in hospitalization. During lunch, the patient shows signs of difficulty breathing and asks for help.</p> <p>Patient history: no pre-existing conditions Medication: no medication</p>																																																											
 Information for Instructors	<p>Patient develops an allergic reaction to the apple (or nuts) in the meal she is eating. Rapid progress with respiratory distress and hypotension. All the patricians will start within in the green area.</p>																																																											
 Instructor team	2x Simulation instructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse																																																											
 Scenario Issues	Anaphylactic reaction with obstructed airway / circulatory problems																																																											
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical incident is identified quickly • Patient is attended within adequate time • Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time • Classification of anaphylaxis • Medical Management kits are used correctly • Correct use of the drop-through 																																																											
 Material / Simulation Equipment	<p>Preparations for green area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vital parameter monitor • Defibrillator • Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator • i.v. / infusion / syringe pump / ampoule kit (adrenalin, corticoids) • Diagnostic kit • Crash cart • Two syringe pumps 	<p>Preparations for red area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient Simulator (SimMan 3G) or actor (+ Intubation mannequin) with possibility to place an i.v. cannula / infusion - which is not at place in the beginning) • Stretcher / Bed beside the transparence screen • Meal with an apple / peanut 	<p>Gimmicks/Requisites</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal Protective Equipment 3x 																																																									
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 Scenario Saver	<p>Too easy: progress of airway swelling with difficult airway (need for surgical airway)</p> <p>Too difficult: fast response to adrenaline and mild anaphylaxis</p>																																																											

<p>Specials / Debriefing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Stop the allergenic• Criteria to identify a critical ill patient• Adequate treatment should be provided or handed through the transparency screen.• Medical Management kits are used correctly (EpiPen, ...)• Treatment of anaphylaxis• Classification of allergic reactions<ul style="list-style-type: none">Stage I: Itchiness, flushing, urticaria, angioedemaStage II: " + light general symptoms (nausea, dyspnea, hypotension)Stage III: " + heavy general symptoms, shockStage IV: Cardiac arrest• Therapy by ERC guidelines (medications and volume)• Medical Management kits are used correctly• Correct use of the drop-through
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Medical Scenario 2: Anaphylactic reaction with obstructed airway - No staff in red area

Medical Scenario 2		Success indicator																																																											
 Patient information	Brian Bwambale	Age	46 y																																																										
		Height	185 cm																																																										
		Weight	75 kg																																																										
 Briefing	<p>Patient is isolated in the unit with confirmed pathogen X (airborne transmission) through PCR on day 5 in hospitalization. One physician and one nurse prepared a dose of mAb114 and are currently infusing the patient.</p> <p>Suddenly, the patient develops pyrexia, chills, tachycardia and tachypnoea.</p> <p>Patient history: no pre-existing conditions Medication: no medication</p>																																																												
 Information for Instructors	<p>Patient develops an allergic reaction to the monoclonal antibody. Rapid progress with respiratory distress and hypotension.</p> <p>No nurses are present in the red area, staff needs to be donned before accessing the patient, basic emergency medication is available in the green zone.</p>																																																												
 Instructor team	2x Simulation instructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse																																																												
 Scenario issues	Anaphylactic reaction with obstructed airway / circulatory problems No staff in the red area																																																												
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical incident is identified quickly • Patient is attended within adequate time • Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time • Classification of anaphylaxis • Medical Management kits are used correctly • Correct use of the drop-through 																																																												
 Material / Simulation Equipment	<p>Preparations for green area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vital parameter monitor • Defibrillator • Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator • i.v. / infusion / syringe pump / ampoule kit (adrenalin, corticoids) • Diagnostic kit (• Crash cart • Diagnostic kit (Temperature, Oxygen, ECG, flashlight, ...) if the patient isn't monitories • Two syringe pumps 	<p>Preparations for red area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient Simulator (SimMan 3G) or actor (+ Intubation mannequin) with possibility to place an i.v. cannula / infusion - which is not at place in the beginning) • Stretcher / Bed beside the transparence screen • Meal with an apple / peanut 	<p>Gimmicks/Requisites</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal Protective Equipment 3x • Lunch 																																																										
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<p>Scenario Saver</p>	<p>Too easy: progress of airway swelling with difficult airway (need for surgical airway)</p> <p>Too difficult: fast response to adrenalin and mild anaphylaxis</p>
<p>Specials / Debriefing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Stop the allergenic ● Criteria to identify a critical ill patient ● Adequate treatment should be provided or handed through the transparency screen. ● Medical Management kits are used correctly (EpiPen, ...) ● Treatment of anaphylaxis ● Importance of epinephrine during treatment ● Classification of allergic reactions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stage I: Itchiness, flushing, urticaria, angioedema Stage II: " + light general symptoms (nausea, dyspnea, hypotension) Stage III: " + heavy general symptoms, shock Stage IV: Cardiac arrest ● Therapy by ERC guidelines (medications and volume) ● Medical Management kits are used correctly ● Correct use of the drop-through ● Giving oxygen by mask through the transparency screen

Medical Scenario 3: Multi- Organ dysfunction (Hypoxia/septic shock) in pediatric patient

Medical Scenario 3		Septic shock in pediatric patient																																																											
 Patient information	Cristin Cola	Age	12 m																																																										
		Height	85 cm																																																										
		Weight	10 kg																																																										
 Briefing	<p>You are a Team of four with one physician and one nurse in the red and the green area. Patient is brought to the isolation unit together with his mother, both suspect of infection with pathogen X (airborne transmission). For 2 days both of them are suffering from dyspnea and coughing.</p> <p>Patient history: no pre-existing conditions Medication: no medication</p>																																																												
 Information for Instructors	<p>Within triage the patient's status worsens with altered mental status and progressing signs of dyspnea.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hypoxia due to infection of lower airways Hypotension due to septic shock 																																																												
 Instructor team	2x Simulation instructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse 1x Actor (mother)																																																												
 Scenario issues	2 Organ dysfunctions (Hypoxia and septic shock) in pediatric patient																																																												
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Critical incident is identified quickly Patient is attended within adequate time Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time Medical Management kits are used correctly 																																																												
 Material / Simulation equipment	<p>Preparation for green area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vital parameter monitor Defibrillator Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator i.v. / infusion / syringe pump / ampoule kit (adrenalin, corticoids) Emergency pack (I.V.; Anaphylaxis, ...) Diagnostic kit (Temperature, Oxygen, ECG, flashlight, ...) 	<p>Preparation for red area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patient Simulator (SimBaby) and actor (mother) Stretcher / Bed beside the transparency screen for the mother Small table 	<p>Gimmicks/Requisites</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal Protective Equipment 3x 																																																										
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 Scenario Saver	<p>Too easy: Getting comatose -> need for intubation Too difficult: getting better when given i.v. volume</p>																																																												

<p>Specials / Debriefing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Critical ill pediatric patient is identified quickly● Scores / signs of critical ill pediatric patients● Patient is attended within adequate time● Without risk of self-endangerment of staff● Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time● Treatment of hypoxia and hypovolemia● Medical Management kits are used correctly● Definition of sepsis● Diagnosis of sepsis by the qSOFA / ABCDE - approaches● Diagnostic tools like blood cultures● Possible focus of the infection● Sepsis vs septic shock● Possibility to give fluids and medications through the transperence screen● Medical Management kits are used correctly● Correct use of the drop-through
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Medical Scenario 4: Receiving an ambulance car with a simple walking patient

Medical Scenario 4		Admission of a walking patient																																																		
 Patient information	Doreen Douglas	Age	32 y																																																	
		Height	155 cm																																																	
		Weight	85 kg																																																	
 Briefing	<p>Patient had contact to a patient with pathogen X on a funeral. For 2 days Mrs. Doreen is suffering from mild symptoms like fever, headache, muscle pain</p> <p>Patient history: high blood pressure Medication: no medication</p>																																																			
 Information for Instructors	A patient, ambulatory, in general good clinical condition and cooperative arrives with an ambulance at the IDTM screening area																																																			
 Instructor team	2x Simulation instructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse																																																			
 Scenario issues	General good clinical condition / Scared because of mild symptoms																																																			
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient treatment is performed in a safe and structured way • Patient is attended within adequate time • Patient is successfully screened, triaged and admitted in the IDTM 																																																			
 Material / Simulation equipment	Preparation for green area <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vital parameter monitor • Defibrillator • Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator • i.v. / infusion / syringe pump / ampoule kit • Emergency pack (I.V.; Anaphylaxis, ...) • Diagnostic kit (Temperature, Oxygen, ECG, flashlight, ...) 	Preparation for red area <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actor • Stretcher / Bed beside the transparency screen • Small table 	Gimmicks/Requisites <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Screening area 																																																	
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 Scenario Saver	<p>Too easy: Patient accidently removes mask Too difficult: Patient can be calmed down.</p>																																																			

Specials /
Debriefing

- Criteria to identify a critical ill patient
- Patient is attended within adequate time
- Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time
- Did the patient follow the planned pathway?
- Any safety incidents?
- Adapted screening and admission of a patient to the IDTM
- Which diagnostic tools should be in red or green area

Medical Scenario 5: Receiving an ambulance car with a complex patient on a wheel chair

Medical Scenario 5		Admission of a patient on a wheel chair																																																											
 Patient information	Ericana Eiden	Age	32 y																																																										
		Height	185 cm																																																										
		Weight	105 kg																																																										
 Briefing	<p>The patient had contact to a patient with pathogen X on a funeral of his wife. For 2 days moderate symptoms with fever, headache, muscle pain, since today general fatigue and dizziness</p> <p>Patient history: high blood pressure Medication: no medication</p>																																																												
 Information for Instructors	A patient with general fatigue and dizziness arrives with an ambulance at the IDTM screening area, not able to walk																																																												
 Instructor team	2x Simulation instructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse																																																												
 Scenario issues	General fatigue and dizziness / not able to walk (Transport on stretcher) Lost his wife on pathogen X																																																												
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient treatment is performed in a safe and structured way • Patient is attended within adequate time • Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time 																																																												
 Material / Simulation equipment	<p>Preparations for green area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vital parameter monitor • Defibrillator • Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator • i.v. / infusion / syringe pump / ampoule kit (adrenalin, corticoids) • Diagnostic kit • Crash cart • Diagnostic kit • Two syringe pumps • Stretcher / Bed • Vital parameter monitor 	<p>Preparations for red area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actor (patient) • Stretcher / Bed beside the transparency screen 	<p>Gimmicks/Requisites</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Screening area 																																																										
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<p>Scenario Saver</p>	<p>Too easy: Too difficult:</p>
<p>Specials / Debriefing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The IDTM can receive an ambulance and receive a patient that is not ambulatory (i.e. Arriving on a stretcher) ● The ambulance is successfully received, including decontamination of the ambulance (prep. for next transport) and a patient arriving on a stretcher is successfully screened, triaged and admitted in the IDTM ● Criteria to identify a critical ill patient ● Patient is attended within adequate time ● Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time ● Did the patient follow the planned pathway? ● Any safety incidents?

Medical Scenario 6: Panic attack within the red area entering the patient room from outside

Medical Scenario 6		Panic attack				
 Patient information	Franky Friday	Age	32 y			
		Height	185 cm			
		Weight	75 kg			
 Briefing	Patient had contact with a patient with pathogen X. He was a former soldier. For 4 days moderate symptoms with coughing, fever, headache, muscle pain Patient history: post-traumatic stress disorder Medication: no medication					
 Information for Instructors	Within the transfer from screening area to patient room, the patient gets a panic attack after looking at another patient (flash back). Tries to escape from the red area and is in panic.					
 Instructor team	2x Simulation instructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse 1x Actor (patient)					
 Scenario issues	Panic attack within the red area on the way to the patient room					
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient treatment is performed in a safe and structured way • Patient is attended within adequate time • Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time 					
 Material / Simulation equipment	Preparations for green area <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vital parameter monitor • Defibrillator • Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator • i.v. / infusion / syringe pump / ampoule kit (adrenalin, corticoids) • Diagnostic kit • Crash cart • Diagnostic kit • Two syringe pumps • Stretcher / Bed • Vital parameter monitor 	Preparations for red area <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actor (patient) • Stretcher / Bed beside the transparency screen 	Gimmicks/Requisites <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 			
 Simulation Control		Start settings	Process	Under therapy	Anamnesis	
	ECG	Sr	Sr	Sr	S	Symptoms for 4 days
	HF	140 /min	160 /min	90 /min		
	SpO ₂	98 %	98 %	89 %		
	BP	160/ 90 mmHg	160 / 90 mmHg	90 / 50 mmHg	A	-
	etCO ₂	40 mmHg	40 mmHg	40 mmHg	M	-
	RR	45 /min	50 /min	10 /min	P	post-traumatic stress disorder
	Temp.	37,8 °C	°C	°C	L	-
	BG	102 mg/dl	mg/dl	mg/dl	E	-
	Pupils	3 mm / 3 mm LR + / +	4 mm / 4 mm LR + / +	3 mm / 3 mm LR + / +	R	-
	Lung sound: normal Fearful patient is coughing. Feels hot / fever. GCS 15.					
 Scenario Saver	Too easy: Patient tries to remove the staff's PPE Too difficult: Patient reacts to down-talking					

<p>Specials / Debriefing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Criteria to identify a critical ill patient● Patient is attended within adequate time● Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time● Any safety incidents? Staff remains safe while treating the patient● Agitated patient can be managed under safety conditions for the staff from the screening area to the patient room.● How to react to a breach of the transparency screen● Enough spacing for movement of staff from screening to patient room is provided – where to go● Safety for staff is provided● No contamination of any staff-members● No injuries to any staff-members● No contamination / injuries to other patients
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Medical Scenario 7: Intubated patient in delirium

Medical Scenario 7		Agitated Patient																																																											
 Patient information	Garry Green	Age Height Weight	50 y 175 cm 65 kg																																																										
 Briefing	<p>Patient with pathogen X, for 10 days in the IDTM with severe ARDS and has been sedated. Since he is getting better, the sedation is paused to evaluate his neurological status.</p> <p>Patient history: Diabetes mellitus Type 2 Medication: no medication</p>																																																												
 Information for Instructors	Patient suddenly awakes and is very agitated. After a while he breaks one of the gloves of the transparency screen.																																																												
 Instructor team	2x Simulation instructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse 1x Actor (patient)																																																												
 Scenario issues	Patient awakes agitated and confused – aggressive against medical staff - breaking the glove																																																												
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Patient treatment is performed in a safe and structured way ● Patient is attended within adequate time ● Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time ● No contamination of any staff-members ● No injuries to any staff-members ● No contamination / injuries to other patients. Patient is stabilized / calmed down with adequate treatment (talk down / medication). Enough spacing for stuff is provided 																																																												
 Material / Simulation equipment	<p>Preparations for green area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Vital parameter monitor ● Defibrillator ● Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator ● i.v. / infusion / syringe pump / ampoule kit (adrenalin, corticoids) ● Emergency pack (I.V.; Anaphylaxis, Intubation, ...) ● Diagnostic kit (Temperature, Oxygen, ECG, flashlight, ...) ● Tape / cable tie 	<p>Preparations for red area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Actor ● Stretcher / Bed beside the transparency screen 	<p>Gimmicks/Requisites</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Personal Protective Equipment 3x 																																																										
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<p>Scenario Saver</p>	<p>Too easy: Patient tries also to remove the staff's PPE. Need sedation to calm down Too difficult: Patient reacts to down-talking</p>
<p>Specials / Debriefing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Call for help / further staff. How can the staff from the inside help (e.g. medication? ... ● Protocol for a breach of the transparency screen. (Wir brauchen noch ein Protokoll für Tape oder Kabelbinder) ● Patient is stabilized / calmed down with adequate treatment (talk down / medication) ● Possible medication to sedate ● Agitated patient can be managed under safety conditions for the staff from the screening area to the patient room. ● How to react to breach of the transparency screen ● How can the transparent screen and glove box be repaired? ● Enough spacing for movement of staff from screening to patient room is provided – where to go ● Safety for staff is provided ● No contamination of any staff-members ● No injuries to any staff-members ● No contamination / injuries to other patients ● Treatment of agitated patients / Trigger for agitation

Medical Scenario 8: Hypoxia due to failure of the ventilator after a power breakdown

Medical Scenario 8		Power breakdown																																																																						
 Patient information	Hellen Help	Age Height Weight	46 y 185 cm 75 kg																																																																					
 Briefing	<p>Patient is isolated in the unit with confirmed infection with pathogen X (airborne transmission) on day 7 in quarantine. Intubated and renal replacement therapy for AKI for 6 days. Due to ARDS prone positioning for 2 days. Patient in prone position.</p> <p>Patient history: Diabetes mellitus Type 2, arterial hypertension Medication: Ramipril 5 mg 1-0-0, Insulin 12-0-28 IE</p>																																																																							
 Information for Instructors	Sudden power breakdown with breakdown of ventilator, oxygen concentrator, monitor, dialysis. No staff in the red area, needs to be donned before accessing the patient.																																																																							
 Instructor team	2x Simulation instructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse																																																																							
 Scenario issues	Hypoxia due to respiratory failure and lack of oxygen supply in ventilated patient																																																																							
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical incident is identified quickly • Patient is attended within adequate time • Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time 																																																																							
 Material / Simulation equipment	Preparations for green area <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Isolation Unit • Stretcher / Bed • Vital parameter monitor • Defibrillator • Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator • i.v. / infusion / syringe pump / ampoule kit (adrenalin, corticoids) • Crash cart • Dialysis machine 	Preparations for red area <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient Simulator (SimMan 3G) • Intubated in prone position • i.v. cannula / infusion right forearm 	Gimmicks/Requisites <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal Protective Equipment 3x 																																																																					
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 Scenario Saver	<p>Too easy: no oxygen available Too difficult: emergency power generator starts</p>																																																																							

<p>Specials / Debriefing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Criteria to identify a critical ill patient● Patient is attended within adequate time<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Time needed for donning the PPE and begin of treatment● Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time● Patient care can be provided also during power breakdowns due to disruptive phenomena.● Power-Backup and Oxygen-Backup for critical infrastructure (ventilator/ monitoring) is working on time● Staff can move in adequate time from green to red area to provide patient care.
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Medical Scenario 9: Critical neonate with difficulties in breathing

Medical Scenario 9		Critical neonate with fever																																																											
 Patient information	Irene Itungu	Age	24 y																																																										
		Height	165 cm																																																										
		Weight	85 kg																																																										
 Briefing	<p>Pregnant patient (32nd week of pregnancy, 3rd pregnancy), comes to the unit with high fever, difficulty breathing, general body pain and begin of labor.</p> <p>Patient was brought to the isolation room is treated by a gynecologist, which called you for treating the newborn.</p> <p>Patient history: no pre-existing conditions Medication: no medication</p>																																																												
 Information for Instructors	Rapid birth green amniotic fluid, cyanotic neonate who needs CPAP																																																												
 Instructor team	2x Simulation instructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse																																																												
 Scenario Issues	Critical neonate with difficulties in breathing																																																												
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical incident is identified quickly • Patient is attended within adequate time • Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time • Treatment of 2 patients (mother and neonate) 																																																												
 Material / Simulation equipment	Preparations for green area <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vital parameter monitor • Defibrillator • Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator • i.v. / infusion / syringe pump / ampoule kit (adrenalin, corticoids) • Emergency pack (I.V.; Anaphylaxis, ...) • Diagnostic kit (Temperature, Oxygen, ECG, flashlight, ...) 	Preparations for red area <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient Simulator (SimMan 3G) or actor (+ Intubation mannequin) with possibility to place an i.v. cannula / infusion • Stretcher / Bed beside the transparency screen 	Gimmicks/Requisites <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal Protective Equipment 3x 																																																										
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 Scenario Saver	<p>Too easy: resuscitation of the neonate due to hypoxia</p> <p>Too difficult: neonate adapts spontaneously with adequate breathing</p>																																																												

<p>Specials / Debriefing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Criteria to identify a critical ill patient● Patient is attended within adequate time<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Time needed for donning the PPE and begin of treatment● Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time● Medical Management kits are used correctly
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Medical Scenario 10: Atone hemorrhage with hemodynamic instability

Medical Scenario 10		Atone hemorrhage with hemodynamic instability			
 Patient information	Jeanette James	Age Height Weight	23 y 165 cm 85 kg		
 Briefing	<p>Pregnant patient (39th week of pregnancy, 2nd pregnancy), came to the unit with high fever, difficulty breathing, general body pain and begin of labor. Isolated as suspected. Child was born 10 minutes ago, vaginal birth without abnormalities.</p> <p>Patient history: no pre-existing conditions Medication: no medication</p>				
 Information for Instructors	Extensive vaginal bleeding -> post-partum hemorrhage				
 Instructor team	2x Simulation instructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse				
 Scenario Issues	Atone hemorrhage with hemodynamic instability				
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adaptation of the module to a theater and neonatal unit to have enough space for the possibility to treat 2 patients (mother and neonate) Critical incident is identified quickly Transfusion protocol if available Giving medications (transfusion, syringe pump, etc.) 				
 Material / Simulation equipment	<p>Green Area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Isolation Unit Vital parameters monitor 2x Defibrillator Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator 2x Crash cart (incl. pediatric equipment) Suction unit Transfusion set Syringe pump 	<p>Red Area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actor (mother) Patient Simulator (Newborn Anne) i.v. cannula / infusion right forearm mother already in place Stretcher / Bed Crash cart for newborn (suction, mask, ...) Surgical kit / Ballon-catheter 	<p>Gimmicks/Requisites</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal Protective Equipment 3x 		
 Simulation Control		Mother	Mother	Neonate	Anamnesis
	ECG	Sr	Sr	Sr	S High fever, difficulty breathing, general body pain, begin of labor (4 hours ago)
	HF	140 /min	140 /min	140 /min	
	SpO ₂	88 %	75 %	93 %	
	BP	90/ 50 mmHg	60 / 30 mmHg	70 / 50 mmHg	A -
	etCO ₂	40 mmHg	25 mmHg	40 mmHg	M -
	RR	28 /min	35 /min	45 /min	P -
	Temp.	36,2 °C	35,8 °C	36,2 °C	L 12 hours ago
	BG	102 mg/dl	104 mg/dl	84 mg/dl	E -
	Pupils	3 mm / 3 mm LR + / +	3 mm / 3 mm LR + / +	3 mm / 3 mm LR + / +	R -
	Lung sound: normal Art. BGA: pH 7,21 / Hb 6,4mg/dl / Lac 4,5 / pO ₂ 65 / pCO ₂ 40				
 Scenario Saver	<p>Too easy: severe shock, no response to volume; involving in the treatment of the newborn</p> <p>Too difficult: Stabilization of bleeding</p>				

<p>Specials / Debriefing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Adaption of the room to a theater and a neonatal unit● Criteria to identify a critical ill patient● Patient is attended within adequate time● Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time● Medical Management kits are used correctly● Can two patients be handled in one room?
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Medical Scenario 11: Emergency Cesarean section

Medical Scenario 11		Emergency anesthesia to perform a Cesarean section			
 Patient information	Kristin Kamuhanda	Age Height Weight	25 y 165 cm 85 kg		
 Briefing	<p>Pregnant patient (39th week of pregnancy, 4th pregnancy), came to the unit with high fever, difficulty breathing, general body pain and beginning of labor. She was isolated as a suspected case. Suspicion of fetal distress with fetal bradycardia -> Decision to do a Cesarean section</p> <p>Patient history: no pre-existing conditions Medication: no medication</p>				
 Information for Instructors	Performance of Cesarean section				
 Instructor team	2x Simulation instructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse				
 Scenario issues	Emergency anesthesia to perform a Cesarean section				
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adaptation module to a theater and neonatal unit Critical incident is identified quickly Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time Treatment of 2 patients (mother and neonate) 				
 Material / Simulation equipment	<p>Green Area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vital parameters monitor 2x Defibrillator Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator 2x Crash cart (incl. pediatric equipment) Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator 	<p>Red Area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patient simulator (SimMan) or Actress (with Mama Natalie) Patient Simulator (Newborn Anne) i.v. cannula / infusion right forearm mother Stretcher / Bed Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator 2x Crash cart (incl. pediatric equipment) Suction unit Surgical kit Spinal anesthesia set 	<p>Gimmicks/Requisites</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal Protective Equipment 3x Surgical Equipment Spinal anesthesia simulator 		
 Simulation Control		Mother	Anesthesia	Neonate	Anamnesis
	ECG	Sr	Sr	Sr	S High fever, general body pain
	HF	130 /min	140 /min	140 /min	
	SpO ₂	93 %	88 %	93 %	
	BP	120/ 50 mmHg	90 / 30 mmHg	70 / 50 mmHg	A Allergic to eggs
	etCO ₂	40 mmHg	35 mmHg	40 mmHg	M -
	RR	22 /min	- /min	45 /min	P -
	Temp.	36,2 °C	35,8 °C	36,2 °C	L 5 hours ago
	BG	102 mg/dl	104 mg/dl	84 mg/dl	E -
	Pupils	3 mm / 3 mm LR + / +	3 mm / 3 mm LR + / +	3 mm / 3 mm LR + / +	R -
Lung sound: normal					
 Scenario Saver	<p>Too easy: spinal anesthesia is not working Too difficult: patient stable, procedures can be done easily</p>				

<p>Specials / Debriefing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Position of the bed for the spinal anesthesia (using the staff from the outside by the transparency screen)● Use of the spinal anesthesia● Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time● Medical Management kits are used correctly
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Medical Scenario 12: Peritonsillar abscess with difficult airway – A- Problem

Medical Scenario 12		Peritonsillar abscess with difficult airway																																																											
 Patient information	Lois Lukonso	Age	32 y																																																										
		Height	175 cm																																																										
		Weight	85 kg																																																										
 Briefing	<p>The Patient is admitted after contact with an infected patient at a funeral. Sore throat for 5 days, fever, and increasing dyspnea since today.</p> <p>Patient history: Diabetes Medication: Metformin 1000mg 1-0-1</p>																																																												
 Information for Instructors	Shortly after admission increasing tonsillar swelling with acute dyspnea. Airway problem.																																																												
 Instructor team	2x Simulation instructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse																																																												
 Scenario issues	Peritonsillar abscess with difficult airway																																																												
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Critical incident is identified quickly ● Patient is attended within adequate time ● Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time ● Preparation for difficult airway with RSI 																																																												
 Material / Simulation equipment	<p>Green Area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Vital parameter monitor ● Defibrillator ● Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator ● Video laryngoscope ● Crash cart ● Suction unit ● Surgical kit for difficult airway 	<p>Red Area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Patient simulator (SimMan) ● i.v. cannula / infusion right forearm ● Stretcher / Bed 	<p>Gimmicks/Requisites</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Personal Protective Equipment 4x 																																																										
 Simulation Control	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Start</th> <th>Progress</th> <th>Therapy</th> <th></th> <th>Anamnesis</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>ECG</td> <td>Sr</td> <td>Sr</td> <td>Sr</td> <td rowspan="3">S</td> <td rowspan="3">Dyspnea during lunch</td> </tr> <tr> <td>HF</td> <td>130 /min</td> <td>150 /min</td> <td>140 /min</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SpO₂</td> <td>93 %</td> <td>82 %</td> <td>93 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>BP</td> <td>120/ 50 mmHg</td> <td>160 / 95 mmHg</td> <td>130 / 80 mmHg</td> <td>A</td> <td>No allergies</td> </tr> <tr> <td>etCO₂</td> <td>40 mmHg</td> <td>15 mmHg</td> <td>40 mmHg</td> <td>M</td> <td>-</td> </tr> <tr> <td>RR</td> <td>22 /min</td> <td>50 /min</td> <td>30 /min</td> <td>P</td> <td>-</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Temp.</td> <td>36,2 °C</td> <td>35,9 °C</td> <td>36,2 °C</td> <td>L</td> <td>90 minutes ago</td> </tr> <tr> <td>BG</td> <td>182 mg/dl</td> <td>184 mg/dl</td> <td>184 mg/dl</td> <td>E</td> <td>-</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Pupils</td> <td>3 mm / 3 mm, LR + / +</td> <td>3 mm / 3 mm, LR + / +</td> <td>3 mm / 3 mm, LR + / +</td> <td>R</td> <td>-</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Lung sound: Coughing, Stridor</p>		Start	Progress	Therapy		Anamnesis	ECG	Sr	Sr	Sr	S	Dyspnea during lunch	HF	130 /min	150 /min	140 /min	SpO ₂	93 %	82 %	93 %	BP	120/ 50 mmHg	160 / 95 mmHg	130 / 80 mmHg	A	No allergies	etCO ₂	40 mmHg	15 mmHg	40 mmHg	M	-	RR	22 /min	50 /min	30 /min	P	-	Temp.	36,2 °C	35,9 °C	36,2 °C	L	90 minutes ago	BG	182 mg/dl	184 mg/dl	184 mg/dl	E	-	Pupils	3 mm / 3 mm, LR + / +	3 mm / 3 mm, LR + / +	3 mm / 3 mm, LR + / +	R	-				
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Pupils	3 mm / 3 mm, LR + / +	3 mm / 3 mm, LR + / +	3 mm / 3 mm, LR + / +	R	-																																																								
 Scenario Saver	<p>Too easy: Aspiration with cardiac arrest during intubation or the person inside can't intubate and the anesthesiologist is inside → intubation threw the transparency screen</p> <p>Too difficult: Oxygenation sufficient without intubation over SpO₂ 90%</p>																																																												

<p>Specials / Debriefing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Criteria to identify a critical ill patient● Patient is attended within adequate time● Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time● Medical Management kits are used correctly● How to prepare an RSI in the IDTM - suction, ventilation● Bed positioning for Intubation● Intubation possible through transparent screen?● Rapid Sequence Induction
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Medical Scenario 13: Acute (tension-) pneumothorax – B- Problem

Medical Scenario 13		Breathing problem – acute (tension-) pneumothorax																																																										
 Patient information	Martin Muhindu	Age Height Weight	46 y 195 cm 75 kg																																																									
 Briefing	<p>Patient is isolated in the unit with confirmed infection with pathogen X (airborne transmission) on day 15 in quarantine. Intensified respiratory therapy (endotracheal intubated) for 5 days. In the last 20 minutes the oxygen saturation is dropping. Patient history: Diabetes mellitus Type 2, arterial hypertension Medication: no medication</p>																																																											
 Information for Instructors	Spontaneous rupture of a bulla in emphysema with formation of a spontaneous pneumothorax. In the course development of a tension component with circulatory depression. Breathing Problem.																																																											
 Instructor team	2x Simulation instructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse																																																											
 Scenario issues	Breathing problem – acute (tension-) pneumothorax																																																											
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fast use of the drop-through for the needle Critical incident is identified quickly Patient is attended within adequate time Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time 																																																											
 Material / Simulation equipment	Green Area <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ventilator Vital parameters monitor 2x Defibrillator Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator 2x Crash cart with decompression needle Suction unit Syringe pump Surgical kit for chest tube 	Red Area <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patient simulator (SimMan) Endotracheal intubated -> Ventilator in green zone CVC V. jug. Int. right side, Sedation: ketamine / morphine Stretcher / Bed 	Gimmicks/Requisites <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal Protective Equipment 4x 																																																									
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 Scenario Saver	<p>Too easy: tension pneumothorax with impairment of the circulation Too difficult: no severe tension component</p>																																																											
 Specials / Debriefing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fast use of the drop-threw for the needle Patient is attended within adequate time Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time Medical Management kits are used correctly Drop-through can used fast and safe 																																																											

Medical Scenario 14: Septic shock with critical hypotension – C- Problem

Medical Scenario 14		Septic shock with critical hypotension (e. g. urinary tract infection)																																																										
 Patient information	Nick Nambirige	Age	46 y																																																									
		Height	195 cm																																																									
		Weight	75 kg																																																									
 Briefing	<p>Patient is isolated in the unit with confirmed infection with pathogen X (airborne transmission) on day 15 in hospitalization.</p> <p>Intensified respiratory therapy was performed for 10 days. Extubating was possible 2 days ago. Since today increasingly reduced general condition with disturbance of consciousness.</p> <p>Patient history: Diabetes mellitus Type 2, arterial hypertension Medication: no medication</p>																																																											
 Information for Instructors	Development of septic shock with progressive hypotension in urinary tract infection. Circulation Problem.																																																											
 Instructor team	2x Simulation instructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse																																																											
 Scenario Issues	Septic shock with critical hypotension (e. g. urinary tract infection)																																																											
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical incident is identified quickly • Patient is attended within adequate time • Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time 																																																											
 Material / Simulation equipment	<p>Green Area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vital parameter monitor • Defibrillator • Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator • i.v. / infusion / syringe pump / ampoule kit • Crash cart 	<p>Red Area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient simulator (SimMan) • i.v. cannula / infusion right forearm • Urinary catheter • Stretcher / Bed 	<p>Gimmicks/Requisites</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal Protective Equipment 3x 																																																									
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Pupils	3 mm / 3 mm, LR + / +	3 mm / 3 mm, LR + / +	3 mm / 3 mm, LR + / +	R	-																																																							
 Scenario Saver	<p>Too easy: Patient gets agitated with septic encephalopathy Too difficult: responding to fluid resuscitation well</p>																																																											
 Specials / Debriefing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical ill pediatric patient is identified quickly • Scores / signs of critical ill pediatric patients • Patient is attended within adequate time • Without risk of self-endangerment of staff • Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time • Treatment of hypoxia and hypovolemia 																																																											

- | | |
|--|---|
| | <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Medical Management kits are used correctly● Definition of sepsis● Diagnosis of sepsis by the qSOFA / ABCDE - approaches● Diagnostic tools like blood cultures● Possible focus of the infection● Sepsis vs septic shock |
|--|---|

Medical Scenario 15: Eclamptic seizure in 33rd week of pregnancy – D- Problem

Medical Scenario 15		Eclamptic seizure in 33 rd week of pregnancy																																																											
 Patient information	Olivia Okioma	Age	24 y																																																										
		Height	155 cm																																																										
		Weight	75 kg																																																										
 Briefing	<p>Patient is isolated in the unit with confirmed infection with pathogen X (airborne transmission) on day 5 in hospitalization. Current pregnancy at 33 weeks of gestation Complains of headache, dizziness, fatigue for 2 hours.</p> <p>Patient history: high blood pressure during pregnancy Medication: no medication</p>																																																												
 Information for Instructors	Development of eclamptic seizure. Disability / Neurological Problem.																																																												
 Instructor team	2x Simulation instructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse																																																												
 Scenario issues	Eclamptic seizure in 33rd week of pregnancy																																																												
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical incident is identified quickly • Patient is attended within adequate time • Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time 																																																												
 Material / Simulation equipment	<p>Green Area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stretcher / Bed • Vital parameter monitor • Defibrillator • Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator • Crash cart • Eclamptic seizure treatment kit 	<p>Red Area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actor (pregnant) • i.v. cannula / infusion right forearm • (CTG) 	<p>Gimmicks/Requisites</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal Protective Equipment 3x 																																																										
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BP	170 / 95 mmHg	190/110 mmHg	150 / 80 mmHg	A	No allergies																																																								
etCO ₂	40 mmHg	15 mmHg	40 mmHg	M	-																																																								
RR	25 /min	6 /min	20 /min	P	-																																																								
Temp.	37,9 °C	37,9 °C	37,8 °C	L	4 hours ago																																																								
BG	142 mg/dl	104 mg/dl	84 mg/dl	E	-																																																								
Pupils	3 mm / 3 mm, LR + / +	3 mm / 3 mm, LR + / +	3 mm / 3 mm, LR + / +	R	-																																																								
 Scenario Saver	<p>Too easy: Patient not responding to first-line treatment with status epilepticus Too difficult: good response to first-line treatment</p>																																																												
 Specials / Debriefing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Criteria to identify a critical ill patient • Patient is attended within adequate time • Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time • Medical Management kits are used correctly • Treatment of preeclampsia and eclampsia • Which material shall be in the green area and which material in the red area? 																																																												

Medical Scenario 16: Evacuation of an unconscious patient

Medical Scenario 16		Evacuation																																																										
 Patient information	Paavai Petton	Age	34 y																																																									
		Height	155 cm																																																									
		Weight	55 kg																																																									
 Briefing	<p>Patient is isolated in the unit with confirmed infection with pathogen X (airborne transmission) on day 5 in hospitalization. The Patient tries to repair a power bar by himself and gets an electric shock with flying sparks. Patient is unconscious beside the bed. During inspection of the patient smoke starts to fill the room.</p> <p>Patient history: - Medication: no medication</p>																																																											
 Information for Instructors	Pat. Is unconscious after the electric shock, increasing smoke development inside the treatment module																																																											
 Instructor team	2x Simulation instructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse																																																											
 Scenario issues	Evacuation in case of fire after short circuit with flying sparks and smoke development																																																											
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Critical incident is identified quickly ● Patient is attended within adequate time ● Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time 																																																											
 Material / Simulation equipment	<p>Green Area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Vital parameter monitor ● Defibrillator ● Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator ● Crash cart ● Fire extinguisher ● Evacuation plan 	<p>Red Area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Patient access ● i.v. cannula / infusion right forearm ● Stretcher / Bed 	<p>Gimmicks/Requisites</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Personal Protective Equipment 4x ● Fog machine ● prepared power cable 																																																									
 Simulation Control	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Start</th> <th>Progress</th> <th>Therapy</th> <th colspan="2">Anamnesis</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>ECG</td> <td>Sr, VES</td> <td>Sr, VES</td> <td>Sr</td> <td rowspan="3">S</td> <td rowspan="3"></td> </tr> <tr> <td>HF</td> <td>120 /min</td> <td>120 /min</td> <td>120 /min</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SpO₂</td> <td>91 %</td> <td>86 %</td> <td>93 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>BP</td> <td>150/ 80 mmHg</td> <td>140 / 45 mmHg</td> <td>130 / 80 mmHg</td> <td>A</td> <td>No allergies</td> </tr> <tr> <td>etCO₂</td> <td>40 mmHg</td> <td>45 mmHg</td> <td>40 mmHg</td> <td>M</td> <td>-</td> </tr> <tr> <td>RR</td> <td>30 /min</td> <td>20 /min</td> <td>20 /min</td> <td>P</td> <td>-</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Temp.</td> <td>36,2 °C</td> <td>36,9 °C</td> <td>37,8 °C</td> <td>L</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>BG</td> <td>86 mg/dl</td> <td>104 mg/dl</td> <td>84 mg/dl</td> <td>E</td> <td>-</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Pupils</td> <td>3 mm / 3 mm LR + / +</td> <td>3 mm / 3 mm LR + / +</td> <td>3 mm / 3 mm LR + / +</td> <td>R</td> <td>-</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Lung Sound: vesicular breath sound</p>		Start	Progress	Therapy	Anamnesis		ECG	Sr, VES	Sr, VES	Sr	S		HF	120 /min	120 /min	120 /min	SpO ₂	91 %	86 %	93 %	BP	150/ 80 mmHg	140 / 45 mmHg	130 / 80 mmHg	A	No allergies	etCO ₂	40 mmHg	45 mmHg	40 mmHg	M	-	RR	30 /min	20 /min	20 /min	P	-	Temp.	36,2 °C	36,9 °C	37,8 °C	L		BG	86 mg/dl	104 mg/dl	84 mg/dl	E	-	Pupils	3 mm / 3 mm LR + / +	3 mm / 3 mm LR + / +	3 mm / 3 mm LR + / +	R	-			
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 Scenario Saver	<p>Too easy: malignant arrhythmias with ventricular tachycardia Too difficult: patient wakes up and can obey commands to leave the room on her own.</p>																																																											
 Specials / Debriefing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Criteria to identify a critical ill patient ● Patient is attended within adequate time ● Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time ● Medical Management kits are used correctly ● Evacuation pathways. Order of evacuation 																																																											

Medical Scenario 17: Acute kidney and liver injury requiring intervention (hemodialysis)

Medical Scenario 17		Success indicator		Acute kidney failure is identified by health personal by clinical and point of care lab diagnostics. Lab assessment and hemodialysis in IDTM is possible. Adequate space for the needed biomedical devices is available in the green area.																																																									
 Patient information	Quentina Quarantino		Age	23 y																																																									
			Height	162 cm																																																									
			Weight	63kg																																																									
 Briefing	Patient is isolated in the unit with confirmed infection with pathogen X. She has low temperature, shivers, dysuria, back pain, has bradycardia, edema all over the body and difficulties in breathing. Oxygen saturation has dropped. The point of care lab results shows high creatinine and high liver enzymes plus low 31albumin. Patient history: arterial hypertension Medication: no medication																																																												
 Information for Instructors	Patient has an acute kidney injury following a liver failure with life-threatening hypoglycemia. The diagnostic includes a point of care diagnostic which shows the relevant parameters and there was urine output of 50 ml for the last twenty hours.																																																												
 Instructor team	2x Simulation instructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse																																																												
 Scenario issues	AKI – acute kidney injury and liver injury requiring medical and mechanical intervention (hemodialysis)																																																												
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> point of care lab testing needs to performed early enough medical treatment for treatment of life-threatening electrolyte decompensation needs to be performed in time hemodialysis needs to be prepared / ordered in time, cannula (dialysis catheter) needs to be administered rapidly. 																																																												
 Material / Simulation equipment	Green Area <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vital parameter monitor Defibrillator Shaldon Catheter, catheterization set hemodialysis machine Oxygen / Airway / Ventilator i.v. / infusion / syringe pump / ampoule kit (adrenalin, corticoids) Diagnostic kit Crash cart Diagnostic kit (Temperature, Oxygen, ECG, flashlight, ...) if the patient isn't monitors Two syringe pumps 		Red Area <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patient simulator (SimMan) i.v. cannula / infusion right forearm Stretcher / Bed (Shaldon – already prepared) 		Gimmicks/Requisites <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal Protective Equipment 4x 																																																								
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 Scenario Saver	<p>Too easy: patient is getting unconscious</p> <p>Too difficult: recovery after medical treatment and no hemodialysis</p>																																																												

<p>Specials / Debriefing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Criteria to identify an organ failure● Patient is attended within adequate time● Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time● lab diagnostics are available in time● catheterization inside of the isolation area● Lab assessment and hemodialysis in IDTM is possible● Adequate space for the needed biomedical devices is available in the green area
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2. The Logistic Scenarios

Overview

Scenario	Topic
Logistic Scenario 1	Transporting the IDTM to any location
Logistic Scenario 2	Setting up the IDTM
Logistic Scenario 3	Cleaning and disinfecting the IDTM
Logistic Scenario 4	Dismantling and re-packing the IDTM

Logistic Scenario 1: Transporting the IDTM to any location

Logistic Scenario 1	Transport		
 Briefing	<p>The IDTM is stored in the warehouse and an alert is declared. A site has been identified and the team need to deploy with the IDTM. The team moves the IDTM from the warehouse to the set-up site using maximum 2 open vans. The road ensure access by van up to 100 meters to the set-up site.</p>		
 Information for Instructors	<p>Participants will have to manually load the IDTM in the van. Drive up to 100 meters to the set-up site, manually offload the IDTM from the van(s) and transport by foot to the set-up site.</p>		
 Instructor team	1x Simulation instructor 1x Logistician		
 Scenario issues	<p>Volume and weight of the IDTM may be a challenge for its deployment</p>		
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to transport the IDTM, • How to load and offload the IDTM 		
 Material / Simulation equipment	<p style="text-align: center;">Materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IDTM • 2 open vans • 2 ATVs • Identified construction site 	<p style="text-align: center;">Participants / Simulator</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants (at least 2 with driving license) 	<p style="text-align: center;">Gimmicks/Requisites</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work gloves for each participant
 Simulation Control	<p>Different transport means (Van, pick-up, truck) Length of walking distance Availability of forklift</p>		
 Specials / Debriefing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IDTM can be transported in any type road, regardless of the means of transportation. • The IDTM can be transported without vehicle assistance as far as needed. • IDTM is able to be divided into multiple parcels to allow easy transport - transportable by hand if needed • IDTM can resist extreme weather events during transport and other phenomena (waterproof, rodents, etc.) • IDTM can be transported easily with limited transport means • IDTM can resist extreme weather events during transport and other phenomena (waterproof, rodents, etc.) 		

Logistic Scenario 2: Build up the IDTM

Logistic Scenario 2		Build up	
 Briefing	The IDTM is available on the construction site. The team is requested to set it up and no instructions are provided. Nobody from the team has experience with the IDTM		
 Information for Instructors	Participants will have to set up the IDTM without Manufacturer Instructions. The team can ask for some basic tools such as hammer, screwdriver, etc.		
 Instructor team	1x Simulation instructor 1x Logistician		
 Scenario issues	The Manufacturer Instructions are not provided to the participants		
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How to set up the IDTM 		
 Material / Simulation equipment	Materials <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IDTM Basic tools Identified construction site 	Participants / Simulator <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants 	Gimmicks/Requisites <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Work gloves for each participant
 Simulation Control	Availability of instruction to set up the IDTM Number of participants Experienced participants amongst the team		
 Specials / Debriefing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IDTM can be set up without Manufacturer Instructions IDTM can be set up without tools The IDTM is correctly set up without manufacturer instructions within 4 hours 		

Logistic Scenario 3: Cleaning up the IDTM

Logistic Scenario 3		Cleaning up	
 Briefing	The Ministry of Health declare the end of the outbreak. The team needs to clean disinfect the IDTM and make it ready for re-packing.		
 Information for Instructors	Participants will have to clean disinfect the IDTM following the correct process.		
 Instructor team	1x Simulation instructor 1x Logistician/WASH		
 Scenario Issues	IDTM proper cleaning and disinfection may be a challenge		
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How to clean and disinfect the IDTM 		
 Material / Simulation equipment	Materials <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IDTM Sprayer PPE Disinfectant Cleaning tools (including floor water squeegee) 	Participants / Simulator <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants 	Gimmicks/Requisites <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cleaning gloves
 Simulation Control	Starting level of cleanliness Availability of trained staff		
 Specials / Debriefing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cleaning and disinfection of the IDTM can be undertaken to IPC standard The IDTM is easy to clean regardless of the use of manufacturer instructions. 		

Logistic Scenario 4: Dismantle and Re-pack the IDTM

Logistic Scenario 4		Dismantle/Re-pack	
 Briefing	The team is requested to dismantle and re-pack and no instructions are provided. Nobody from the team has experience with the IDTM		
 Information for Instructors	Participants will have to dismantle and re-pack the IDTM without instructions. The team can ask for some basic tools such as hammer, screwdriver, etc.		
 Instructor team	1x Simulation instructor 1x Logistician		
 Scenario Issues	The Manufacturer Instructions are not provided to the participants		
 Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How to dismantle and re-pack the IDTM 		
 Material / Simulation equipment	Materials <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IDTM Basic tools 	Participants / Simulator <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants 	Gimmicks/Requisites <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Work gloves for each participant
 Simulation Control	Availability of instruction to dismantle and re-pack the IDTM Number of participants Experienced participants amongst the team		
 Specials / Debriefing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The IDTM is correctly dismantled and re-packed without manufacturer instructions within half day IDTM can be dismantled and re-packed without tools 		